

THE FRIEDEL-CRAFTS REACTION OF NAPHTHALENE WITH BENZENE- AND *p*-TOLUENE-SULPHONYL CHLORIDE

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The Friedel-Crafts reaction of naphthalene with benzene- and *p*-toluene-sulphonyl chloride has been studied in the presence of different catalysts (aluminium, stannic, ferric and zinc chlorides) and different solvents (nitrobenzene, methylene chloride, ethylene chloride and carbon tetrachloride). The product generally is a mixture of the α - and β -naphthylsulphones. The ratio of the isomers varies with experimental conditions. The optimum temperature for the reaction varies with the catalyst and solvent. The α -substitution is greater below 100°, but negligible above 200°.

Naphthalene usually affords a mixture of α - and β - isomers in substitution reactions. The ratio of the two isomers can be considerably varied by altering the experimental conditions. The Friedel-Crafts acylations are reported to be influenced more by the nature of the reagent and solvent than by the temperature (Gore, *Chem. Rev.*, 1955, 55, 242). Where the reagent is bulky, the entropy of activation for α -substitution will be considerably reduced, facilitating β -substitution. The solvent effect is more difficult to understand. It can be due to the solvent solvating or forming complexes with the reagents or transition states. Thus, the need for more experimental data to understand the solvent and steric effects is obvious.

The Friedel-Crafts reactions of naphthalene with arene-sulphonyl chlorides has not been well investigated (vide Beckurts and Otto, *Ber.*, 1878, 11, 2066; Chrustschoff, *Ber.*, 1874, 7, 1167; Huismann, D.R.P. 701954/1941). The results of these workers, however, indicate that the catalyst used can control orientation. Hence, it appeared to be of interest to make a detailed study of this reaction, using different solvents.

Benzene- and *p*-toluene-sulphonyl chlorides were used for the investigation. The catalysts employed were aluminium chloride, stannic chloride, ferric chloride and zinc chloride. The solvent influence was studied with nitrobenzene, carbon tetrachloride, methylene chloride and ethylene chloride. In almost all cases the reaction furnished a mixture of the isomeric α - and β -naphthylsulphones, though the ratio of the isomers varied considerably with experimental conditions. The ratio of the isomers in each mixture was determined from the melting point—composition curve. The compositions, thus arrived at, were checked spectrophotometrically in many cases. Table I summarises the results obtained.

In the absence of a solvent the temperature, most suitable for each catalyst, was as follows: AlCl_3 , 100-10°; FeCl_3 , 100-10°; SnCl_4 , 130-40°; ZnCl_2 , 200-10°. Higher temperatures generally led to the formation of a black material. At lower temperatures the reaction was slow. With the data, thus obtained at different temperatures, it is not possible to correlate the yield with the catalyst. For example, the higher yields obtained with stannic chloride and zinc chloride cannot be ascribed to the greater efficiency of the catalyst, since in both cases higher temperatures were also employed.

The mixtures obtained with catalysts other than zinc chloride contained more of the α -isomer. The product with zinc chloride was mostly the β -isomer (95%). This is in accordance with the well-known fact that higher temperatures favour β -substitution. Even in the case of the Friedel-Crafts acylation of naphthalene, increased yields of the β -isomer were obtained at higher temperatures (Roux, *Ann. chim.*, 1887, vi, 12, 289; Claus and Tersteegen, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1890, 42, 517; Caille, *Compt. rend.*, 1911, 163, 393; Baddeley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 5101).

The influence of solvent was studied with nitrobenzene, methylene chloride, ethylene chloride and carbon tetrachloride, using aluminium chloride as catalyst in each case. Here again, certain difficulties were encountered to collect data under comparable conditions. For example, the reaction did not occur in nitrobenzene to any appreciable extent at low temperatures. With the other solvents, higher temperatures led to dark products which could not be purified.

The results obtained with methylene chloride, ethylene chloride and carbon tetrachloride offer a more interesting study. Here the data are comparable, the experimental conditions being identical. At a given temperature the yield does not seem to depend much on the solvent. With increase of temperature the yield is also raised. The products obtained in these solvents contain chiefly the α -isomer, the one obtained in ethylene chloride being exclusively the α -isomer. Here again, the higher content of the α -isomer cannot be wholly ascribed to the solvent. The temperature seems to have a greater control over the α : β ratio. The solvent effect, even if it exists, does not seem to be significant. A thorough analysis of all the results seems to reveal that the arene-sulphonyl chlorides react with naphthalene primarily at the α -position below 100°, the β -position being increasingly favoured above 100°. The α -substitution is negligible above 200°.

TABLE I

The Friedel-Crafts reaction of arene-sulphonyl chlorides with naphthalene.

Catalyst.	Solvent.	Temp.	Yield.	M.P. of the product.	Ratio of α - and β - isomers by	
					M.P. method.	Spectrophotometric method.
A. With benzenesulphonyl chloride.						
AlCl ₃	None	100-10°	68%	80-82°	65: 35	65: 35
SnCl ₄	"	130-40°	75	82-85°	69: 31	70: 30
FeCl ₃	"	100-10°	64	78-82°	52: 48	53: 47
ZnCl ₂	"	20°	85	114-15°	5: 95	3: 97
AlCl ₃	PhNO ₂	140-60°	86	112-14°	7: 93	...
SnCl ₄	"	"	56	108-12°	10: 90	...
FeCl ₃	"	130-40°	73	104-106°	17: 83	...
AlCl ₃	CH ₂ Cl ₂	30°	20	93-95°	91: 9	93: 7
"	C ₂ H ₄ Cl ₂	"	25	99-101°	100: 0	100: 0
"	CCl ₄	"	18	90-92°	83: 17	"

TABLE I (contd.)

Catalyst.	Solvent.	Temp.	Yield.	M.P. of the product	Ratio of α - and β - isomers by	
					M.P. method.	Spectropho- metric method.
B. with <i>p</i> -toluenesulphonyl chloride.						
AlCl ₃	None	100-10°	59%	105-10°	65:35	64:36
SnCl ₄	"	130-40°	76	102-106°	76:24	73:27
FeCl ₃	"	100-10°	62	107-108°	82:18	85:15
ZnCl ₂	"	200°	89	159-60°	4:96	3:97
AlCl ₃	PhNO ₂	140-60°	86	145-50°	15:85	...
SnCl ₄	"	"	64	144-47°	17:83	...
FeCl ₃	"	130-40°	67	152-55°	10:90	...
AlCl ₃	CH ₂ Cl ₂	45°	58	100-102°	71:29	66:34
"	C ₂ H ₄ Cl ₂	"	60	119-20°	100:0	100:0
"	CCl ₄	"	63	107-108°	81:19	87:13

EXPERIMENTAL

Analysis of Mixtures of α - and β -Naphthylsulphones.—The ratio of the α - and β -isomers in each mixture was determined from the melting point-composition curve. Synthetic mixtures of the pure isomers were prepared and their m. p. determined. These mixtures did not generally have a sharp m.p. but melted through a range. The point at which almost a clear liquid resulted was taken as the m.p. of the mixture. The variation of the m.p. with composition for the mixtures of α - and β -naphthylphenylsulphones and α - and β -naphthyl-*p*-tolylsulphones is given below.

TABLE II

	α - & β -Naphthylphenylsulphones.						α - & β -Naphthyl- <i>p</i> -tolylsulphones.					
α (%)	100	90	80	70	60	55	100	90	80	70	60	50
M.P.	100°	95°	89°	84°	79°	78°	120°	114°	107°	101°	105°	114°
β (%)	100	90	80	70	60	50	100	90	80	70	60	
M.P.	117.5°	110°	103°	96°	89°	81°	163.5°	153°	144°	134°	123°	

These data were used to analyse sulphone mixtures obtained. In cases where the m.p. indicated two possible compositions, small amounts of pure α - and β -isomers were added separately to the mixture and the m.p. redetermined. If a mixture is richer in α -isomer, its m.p. will be raised by small additions of α -sulphone and depressed by small additions of β -sulphone.

The quantitative estimation of the components of a mixture by the spectrophotometric method depends upon the fact that the total extinction of any mixture is a summation of the separate extinctions of the components (Gillam and Stern, "An Introduction to Electronic Absorption Spectroscopy in Organic Chemistry", Edward Arnold, London, 1954, p. 185). The absorption curves of α - and β -naphthylphenylsulphones (Fig. 2) and also those of α - and β -naphthyl-*p*-tolylsulphones (Fig. 1) were plotted and the compositions of the mixtures were determined by finding the extinction at suitable wave-lengths.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

General Procedure for the Friedel-Crafts Reaction.—A mixture of naphthalene (0.1 *M*), benzene- or *p*-toluene-sulphonyl chloride (0.1 *M*) and the catalyst (0.15 *M*) was heated to and kept at the required temperature (see Table I) for 30-40 minutes. The product was cooled and decomposed with HCl (dil.). The mixture of α - and β -naphthylsulphones, thus obtained, was recrystallised from ethanol. The α : β ratio was then determined.

When the reaction was carried out in various solvents, the amounts of solvents used and the duration of the reaction (given in parentheses) were as follows: nitrobenzene, 75 c.c. (30 minutes); methylene chloride, ethylene chloride or carbon tetrachloride, 200 c.c. (2 hrs. in the case of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and 15 hours in the case of benzenesulphonyl chloride).

Preparation of Sulphones.— α -Naphthylphenylsulphone was prepared by the permanganate oxidation of α -naphthylphenyl sulphide. The latter was prepared from thiophenol and α -bromonaphthalene by the Mauthner method.

β -Naphthylphenylsulphone was similarly prepared starting from β -thionaphthol and iodobenzene.

Similar procedures were adopted for the preparation of the *p*-tolylsulphones. β -Naphthyl-*p*-tolylsulphone melted at 163-64°. Hans Meyer (*Annalen*, 1923, 423, 327), who prepared it by passing the vapours of toluene over β -naphthalenesulphonic acid at 150°, reports m.p. 154°.

Ultraviolet Absorption Measurements.—The ultraviolet absorption spectra were determined with a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer, Model DU. The solvent used was 95% ethanol, purified by distillation after treatment with lead acetate and sodium hydroxide.

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